

UK-CTAP briefing on Ivermectin [originally codified 14 December 2020]

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CAVEAT: The UK COVID-19 Therapeutics Advisory Panel was convened to review and select potential COVID-19 therapeutics for publicly funded clinical trials. Briefs were prepared by the UKRI Secretariat Due Diligence Team to support the work of the Panel. The aim of briefs was to summarise and qualify the evidence for candidate drugs proposed by industry, academia and the general public through an open portal. Briefs were prepared rapidly to meet tight deadlines in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. They reflect the state of knowledge regarding COVID-19 and drug candidate at the date of completion (Chinnery et al., 2021).

This brief is published for transparency and historical record and should not be understood as a peer reviewed scientific publication. The date of completion is marked and it is redacted where commercial sensitivities are involved.

1. Proposed products

Ivermectin is a semisynthetic anthelmintic that is derived from the avermectins, a class of highly active broad-spectrum, anti-parasitic agents isolated from the fermentation products of *Streptomyces avermitilis*.

Ivermectin is included on the list of WHO essential medicines (WHO, 2019).

In the UK, ivermectin for human use is only authorised as cream for topical use for the topical treatment of inflammatory lesions of rosacea (papulopustular) in adult patients.

An oral tablet can be imported from France (Stromectol 3mg tablets). Generic forms are available in Europe. These are indicated for the treatment of gastrointestinal strongyloidiasis (anguillulosis), the treatment of suspected or diagnosed microfilaraemia in patients with lymphatic filariasis due to *Wuchereria bancrofti*, and the treatment of human sarcoptic scabies.

Inhaled and nebulized Ivermectin has been suggested by a number of authors, but no licenced or existing nebulised or inhaled versions of the drug exist in licenced use (Chaccour et al., 2020).

Of note there is significant veterinary use of Ivermectin in the UK, so drug acquisition is unlikely to be a problem.

Full information on formulations, posology and safety from regulatory documents is summarised in Appendix section 9.

2. Rationale for development in COVID-19

Ivermectin is an anti-helminthic drug used widely across the world in animals and humans; the WHO has estimated that almost 1/3 of the world's population has been treated with it at some point in their lives (approx. 300 million doses per year). Its primary mechanism of action for its main indication is allosteric inhibition of glutamate-gated chloride channels in nerves and muscles of parasites. At human therapeutic doses the affinity of the drug to animal or human receptors is about 100 times lower than those in the targeted helminth, allowing for a wide therapeutic window. However, at very high doses (potentially required for antiviral efficacy) there could be a toxicity concern in humans.

2.1. Anti-inflammatory activity

The evidence for an anti-inflammatory effect of ivermectin is derived from a combination of pre-clinical in vitro and in vivo studies. Overall the mechanism is thought to be through inhibition of the NF- κ B/MAPK pathway leading to suppression of TNF-alpha and IL-6 inflammatory responses which drive macrophage/neutrophil chemotaxis, NETosis and a skewed inflammatory response leading to cytokine storm in moderate and severe COVID-19 lung disease. Evidence from cancer cell line models points to Ivermectin directly binding EGFR upstream of NF- κ B/MAPK and competitively inhibiting its signalling.

It has also been speculated that ivermectin may exert more downstream effects that may interfere with other pro-inflammatory signalling pathways e.g. the interaction between damage-associated molecular pattern high mobility group box 1 (HMGB1) and the TLR4 receptor, which has been suggested to mediate COVID-19-associated lung inflammation (Andersson et al., 2020). This has raised the question of whether ivermectin at or modestly above the standard clinical dose, may prove efficacious in treating disorders associated with lung injury and cytokine storm, such as COVID-19 (diNicolantonio et al., 2020).

In a preprint study, ivermectin has been tested in golden hamsters inoculated intranasally with SARS-CoV-2 (de Melo et al., 2020). At the time of infection, the treatment group received a subcutaneous injection of ivermectin at the anti-parasitic dose of 400 μ g/kg; the control group received saline. Viral RNA load in the respiratory tract was unchanged by ivermectin; by contrast there was impact on the virus-induced inflammatory response, although findings appeared mixed. In hamster nasal turbinates, ivermectin resulted in downregulation of IL-6, IL-10, TNF α and CXCL10 in the females, whilst males showed upregulation in proinflammatory IFN γ and CCL5. In lung tissue, both sexes showed upregulation of IL-10. Finally, the IL-6/IL-10 ratio was lower in the ivermectin group vs saline-treated hamsters – of interest because lower plasma IL-6/IL-10 ratios have been reported in hospitalised COVID-19 patients not requiring intensive care (McElvaney 2020). Clearly these in vivo findings need further validation, as well as clarification regarding the sex differences. It should also be noted that the administration of ivermectin at the same time as the infective challenge in this model may have less relevance to the clinical context of treating the hyperinflammatory response to COVID-19.

The same study also measured clinical outcomes, the main one being hamster loss of smell (hyposmia or anosmia as measured by the buried food finding test). 66.7% of saline-treated hamsters presented with hyposmia or anosmia vs 22.2% in the ivermectin group ($p=0.018$); this

effect was more dramatic in females vs males (Figure 1). Dose-response analysis in the male subgroup showed that the lower ivermectin dose (100/200 ug/kg) elicited similar clinical outcomes as the anti-parasitic dose of 400 ug/kg), but how this translates to humans is unclear.

a. All infected hamsters

b. Infected males

c. Infected females

Figure 1: Clinical presentation and olfaction test of SARS-CoV-2-infected hamsters with and without ivermectin treatment .a. clinical signs and olfactory deficit in all infected hamsters. b, clinical signs and olfactory deficit in infected male hamsters only. c, clinical signs and olfactory deficit in infected female hamsters only. The clinical score is based on a cumulative 0-4 scale: ruffled fur; slow movements; apathy; stress when manipulated. The olfaction test is based on the buried food finding test. Curves represent the percentage of animals that did not find the buried food. Food finding assays were performed at 3 days post-infection. Mann-Whitney test at 4 dpi (clinical signs) and Logrank (Mantel-Cox) test (olfaction tests). The p value is indicated in bold when significant at a 0.05 threshold. Symbols indicate the median \pm interquartile range. Data were obtained from three independent experiments for males and two independent experiments for females (de Melo et al., 2020).

Aside from the COVID-19 setting, ivermectin has been studied in LPS challenged C57BL/6 mice (intraperitoneal LPS at a lethal dose of 32 mg/kg). When 4 mg/kg ivermectin was administered to mice 2h before the LPS challenge, mortality of mice was reduced by 50%. While mechanism of action was unclear, ivermectin did significantly decrease the production of TNF α , IL-1 β and IL-6 both in vivo and in vitro. NF- κ B nuclear translocation was also suppressed (Zhang et al., 2008). A recent report suggests that the 4mg/kg dose of ivermectin used in the above studies would result in a human adjusted dose of about 36 mg if extrapolated to a 70 kg human (DiNicolantonio et al., 2020).

Ivermectin has also been reported to inhibit the production of nitric oxide (NO) and prostaglandin 2 (PGE2) when murine RAW 264.7 macrophages were challenged with LPS in vitro (Zhang et al., 2009). A subsequent study in the same macrophage cell line (RAW 264.7 cells) found that ivermectin (0.625 to 5 mg/L) inhibited LPS-induced production of inflammatory cytokines by blocking NF- κ B and MAPK (Ci et al., 2009).

In a murine asthma model, in which allergic airway inflammation and airway remodelling is induced by ovalbumin challenge, ivermectin (2 mg/kg) was shown to inhibit the recruitment of immune cells, production of cytokines in the bronchoalveolar lavage fluids and secretion of OVA-specific IgE and IgG1 in the serum. The pulmonary histology of the mice indicated that ivermectin might suppress mucus hypersecretion by goblet cells in the airway (Yan et al., 2011).

In a murine model of atopic dermatitis, induced by repeated exposure to the allergen *Dermatophagoides farinae*, ivermectin (2 mg/kg) was shown to inhibit T-cell priming and activation and production of inflammatory cytokines. In contrast, ivermectin had no effect on dendritic cells in vivo and in vitro (Ventre et al., 2017).

Wound healing was the outcome of interest in studies with ivermectin cream (0.03–1%) in male Sprague Dawley rats. Compared to a vehicle control, ivermectin was found to improve the time to heal rate. Furthermore, it was found that ivermectin modulated the inflammatory response by increasing levels of proinflammatory IL-1 α and TNF- α in the first stages of wound healing and then later decreasing the same levels to promote healing (Sia et al., 2020).

3. Pharmacology

Studies on the anti-inflammatory effects of Ivermectin are almost exclusively in rodent models. The actual drug concentrations required to achieve specific anti-inflammatory effects are often not explicit, though the doses used are available. Unfortunately, there is no direct evidence to infer human drug PK for Ivermectin based on rodent data, and no clear evidence for a dose equivalence factor for the drug. Consequently, to decide if a given dose in rodents has potential efficacy in humans some dosing assumptions will need to be made. If linear dosing by weight is assumed (ie. the mg/kg dose in mice is the same as the mg/kg dose in humans) then standard clinical doses (0.2-0.4 mg/kg) are likely to have significant effects on cytokine levels and inflammation. Notably the EMA and FDA have recognised that PK in humans and animals are significantly different, and there is some support for a linear dosing equivalence from the hamster study mentioned in section 3. Most notably the veterinary dose of 0.2 mg/kg (as for humans) is the same in horses, cattle, cats and swine lending more weight to a genuine dose equivalence across species without needing BSA correction.

3.1. Preclinical pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics summary

- In wild type mice, 0.2mg/kg oral dose led to 71 ± 56 nM (i.e. 62 ± 49 µg/L) plasma concentration at 2h (Figure 2): variability between mouse subjects was very large (Kiki-Mvouaka S et al, 2009)
- This is similar to the clinical peak plasma concentration reached after 14-day daily oral dosing at 300µg/kg (Figure 3 left)
- 4mg/kg oral dose in mice reduced lipopolysaccharide-induced mortality by 50% (Zhang X, et al, 2008). However, the mouse plasma concentration at this dose might not be clinically achievable. Hence, this experiment may not be used as strong evidence to support ivermectin use for treating COVID-19
- Hamster PK is unknown. If the 400 µg/kg dose used in the study by de Melo et al., 2020 generated plasma PK that is similar to the clinical dose, then it suggests ivermectin might be effective as an anti-inflammatory agent for COVID-19.

3.2. Clinical pharmacokinetics summary

- Ivermectin plasma PK was measured and modelled in patients with uncomplicated malaria in Kenya (Smit *et al*, 2019)
 - 3-day oral QD regimens at 300 µg/kg dose and 600 µg/kg dose were best recapitulated with 2-compartment model (original diagram: Figure 9. Reproduced: Figure 10)
 - These doses generated plasma concentrations lower than 300nM (Figure 3); peak concentrations were not sustained, and plasma concentration returned to baseline within 4-8 hours.

Figure 2. Ivermectin plasma concentration in wild type mice after a single 0.2mg/kg dose is administered orally, plotted in nM in semilog scale (left) and natural scale (right). Data were taken at 2, 5, 8, 24 and 48h post oral administration. Data digitised from Kiki-Mvouaka S et al, 2009.

Figure 3. Simulation of ivermectin plasma PK in adults with uncomplicated malaria in Kenya. 1000 patients were sampled using Latin Hypercube method, assuming bodyweight is in range of 45-101kg with a median of 60kg. A) 300µg/kg PO QD for 14 days. B) 600µg/kg PO QD for 14 days. Red line: expected values. Black lines: 5%-95% percentiles. The 2-compartment model was reproduced from Smit et al, 2019. Parameters were tabulated in the middle column of Table 1 in that paper (i.e. "Ivermectin simultaneous PK/PD model").

4. Evidence

There are many trials in COVID-19 that include ivermectin in monotherapy or combination therapy. Some meta-analyses include up to 24 clinical trials.

It must be noted that currently most trials have not been properly reported: some studies have reported results only on clinicaltrials.gov, others report results on their websites or in preprints. Therefore, it seems difficult to gain overview of the current high-quality evidence.

The current meta-analyses suggest positive effects on mortality (Padhy et al., 2020 and COVID-19 Critical Care Alliance). But unfortunately, these meta-analyses fail to provide adequate evidence for decision making due to the following reasons:

- The scientifically published meta-analysis is already out of date and discusses the inherent weaknesses of the included studies and meta-analysis.
- The meta-analyses in the grey literature contain all studies without selection for quality or bias. No adequate methodology has been reported to re-assure that the results of the meta-analyses are adequate.

4.1. Published meta-analysis in COVID-19

A very preliminary systematic review and meta-analysis has been published as a non-peer-reviewed preprint. It conducted a meta-analysis of two observational and one randomised trial (two of them discussed above). It found an odds ratio of 0.53 ($P = 0.04$) for all-cause mortality in patients receiving ivermectin across 3 studies including 629 patients in total (397 treated). The authors contest high bias and low patient numbers for this study. The meta-analysis did not include the newest data from randomised controlled trials and hence is not up-to date (Padhy et al., 2020).

4.2. Meta-analyses in the grey literature

Since the first consideration of ivermectin by UK-CTAP various efforts have been made to collect meta-analyses on COVID-19 trials that include ivermectin. These are not published in peer-reviewed studies but are published on homepages: Covid-19 critical care alliance ¹ and IVMMETA ².

COVID-19 Critical Care Alliance

The COVID-19 Critical Care Alliance has produced a policy document that summarised the current level of evidence on Ivermectin studies. In this document also meta-analyses are presented for symptomatic infection in the prophylactic setting and mortality in the treatment setting.

¹ <https://covid19criticalcare.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/FLCCC-Ivermectin-in-the-prophylaxis-and-treatment-of-COVID-19.pdf>

² <https://ivmmeta.com/>

Comments:

- No methodology for the meta-analyses has been provided.
- Most studies have not been peer-reviewed and results have been collected from preprints or clinicaltrials.gov.
- No quality control or systematic look for bias in study selection
- Across all trials, the observed odds ratios (OR) are very heterogenous with high confidence intervals. The reported average improvement in all studies therefore might not be of relevance.
- In many trials, ivermectin was not given as monotherapy so it is unclear if the effect can be attributed to ivermectin alone (or any other drugs given as co-medication)

Figure 4: Forest plot of meta-analysis of ivermectin in prophylaxis trials; <https://covid19criticalcare.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/FLCCC-Ivermectin-in-the-prophylaxis-and-treatment-of-COVID-19.pdf>

Figure 5: Forrest plot of meta-analysis of mortality outcomes reported from clinical trials of ivermectin in COVID-19 hospitalized patient; <https://covid19criticalcare.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/FLCCC-Ivermectin-in-the-prophylaxis-and-treatment-of-COVID-19.pdf>

IVMMETA

IVMMETA contains a random-effects meta-analysis of ivermectin in COVID-19 across all stages from pre-exposure prophylaxis to severely hospitalised patients. The data and analyses are compiled by anonymous PhD researchers, scientists, people who hope to make a contribution³. The results are published anonymously on their homepage and they declare receiving no funding.

In terms of methodology, they have automated searches across all major scientific output sites and extract effect sizes and associated data from all studies. If studies report multiple kinds of effects then the most serious outcome is used in calculations for that study, e.g. mortality. Results are all expressed with RR < 1.0 suggesting effectiveness.

Currently they report the following outcomes of random-effects meta-analysis:

- In total 24 studies have been included and all (100%) of studies report positive effects. The probability that an ineffective treatment generated results as positive as the 24 studies to date is estimated to be 1 in 17 million (p = 0.00000006).
- 10 RCTs have been included and all (100%) studies report positive effects, with an estimated reduction of 74% in the effect measured using a random effects meta-analysis, RR 0.26 [0.12-0.56].

Figure 6: Forest plot (random effects model) for Randomized Controlled Trials only

Comments:

- The general choice of a random-effects meta-analysis seems adequate given the large heterogeneity of patients, intervention dose and study designs.
- Most studies have not been peer-reviewed and results have been collected from preprints or clinicaltrials.gov.
- No quality control or systematic look for bias in study selection.
- Across all trials, the observed RR are very heterogenous with high confidence intervals. The reported average improvement in all studies therefore might not be of relevance.

³ <https://c19study.com/faq.html>

- In many trials, ivermectin was not given as monotherapy so it is unclear if the effect can be attributed to ivermectin alone (or any other drugs given as co-medication)

[SECTION REDACTED]1

4.3. Description of individual trials reported in previous version of briefing

At the time of writing the previous briefing only a couple of trials were identified and described in more detail. These are listed below, and the level of detail was kept to provide context in terms of quality of the trials that have read-out.

For the writing of this update, it became clear that there are more trial read-outs in the grey literature, as discussed above in the meta-analysis section.

Ahmed et al., 2020: RCT

- Design: single-centre, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial
- Population:
 - Inclusion: admitted to hospital within the last 7 days with either fever ($\geq 37.5^{\circ}\text{C}$); cough or sore throat; and diagnosed positive for SARS-CoV-2 by rRT-PCR.
 - ITT population: n= 72 patients enrolled 24 per arm (1:1:1 randomisation)
 - 4 people left study (reason unknown) -> FAS (full analysis set) population n=68 (placebo n=23, ivermectin+doxycycline n=23, ivermectin n=22)
 - Authors declare that the pre-treatment characteristics (demographics, clinical history, comorbidity and laboratory values) were comparable among the three treatment groups.
 - Mean age was 42 years, with 54% being female and ill on average 3.83 days before assessment.
 - Fever: placebo (82.6%; n=19/23), ivermectin+doxycycline (73.9%, n=17/23), ivermectin (77.3%, n=17/22)
 - Cough: placebo (65.2%; n=15/23), ivermectin+doxycycline (82.6%; n=19/23), ivermectin (81.8%; n=18/22)
 - Sore throat: placebo (17.4%, n=4/23), ivermectin+doxycycline (13%; n=3/23), ivermectin (18.2%, n=4/22)
- Intervention/control (1:1:1 randomisation):
 - ivermectin monotherapy (oral, 12mg once daily for 5 days)
 - ivermectin in combination with doxycycline (oral 12mg ivermectin single dose and 200mg stat doxycycline day-1 followed by 100mg 12hrly for next 4 days)
 - placebo control
- Outcomes:
 - Declared primary endpoints: 1) time required for virologic clearance (a negative rRT-PCR result on nasopharyngeal swab); remission of fever ($\geq 37.5^{\circ}\text{C}$); and cough within 7 days.

- Declared other endpoints: patients failing to maintain an SpO₂ >93% despite oxygenation and days on oxygen support; duration of hospitalization; and all-cause mortality; and safety.
- Results:
 - Primary endpoint
 - Mean duration to viral clearance: placebo (12.7 days; CI= 11.3 - 14.2), ivermectin+doxycycline (11.5 days; CI= 9.8 - 13.2), ivermectin (9.7 days ; CI= 7.8 - 11.8)
 - Kaplan-Meier survival analysis (Figure 7):
 1. Ivermectin day 7: HR =4.1; (CI) = 1.1- 14.7; p=0.03
 2. Ivermectin day 14: HR=2.7; CI= 1.2 - 6.0; p=0.02
 3. Ivermectin+doxycycline day 7: HR=2.3; CI= 0.6 - 9.0; p=0.22
 4. Ivermectin+doxycycline day 14: HR=1.7; CI= 0.8 - 4.0; p=0.19
 - Other endpoints:
 - Mean duration of hospitalisation (p =0.93): placebo (9.7 days; CI= 8.1 - 11.), ivermectin+doxycycline (10.1 days; CI= 8.5 - 11.8), ivermectin (9.6 days; CI= 7.7 - 11.7).
 - Reduction of fever, cough or sore throat are reported. No statistical changes were reported. But it also seems they lost many patients to follow up, so results of these analyses are not useable
 - Safety: None of the patient enrolled required oxygen or had serious adverse drug events recorded.
- Comments:
 - Not yet peer-reviewed
 - Small study without details on blinding or randomisation. The description of baseline characteristics is also limited. Hence there is little assurance that randomisation led to similar patient groups across study arms.
 - The ITT analysis is not provided. Clearly with such a small trial, the exclusion of patients could make a big difference.
 - The absolute treatment effect on viral clearance of ivermectin monotherapy is 3 days. This treatment effect is relatively small (3 days faster viral clearance) and is not contextualised in terms of its clinical relevance. For example, ivermectin had no effect on duration of hospitalisation or reduction of COVID-19 symptoms compared to placebo. Mortality or other endpoints have not been reported.
 - No biological rationale as to why ivermectin monotherapy would be more efficacious as compared to combination therapy.

Figure 7: Bangladesh trial: Kaplan-Meier analysis on time to viral clearance

Rahman et al, 2020: RCT (results from NCT04523831) ^{4 5}.

- Design: single-centre, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial
- Population:
 - Inclusion: mild and moderate COVID-19 infected cases with confirmed COVID-19 infection
 - ITT: 400 patients in total (200 per arm)
 - FAS (completed study): 363 in total (ivermectin+doxycycline n=183, placebo n=180)
- Intervention/control (1:1 randomisation):
 - Ivermectin 6 mg x2 (one single intervention) and Doxycycline 100 mg twice daily for 5 days
 - Placebo
- Primary Outcomes:
 - Number of Patients with Early Clinical Improvement (WHO scale) (7 days)
 - Number of Participants with Late Clinical Recovery (12 days)
- Results:
 - Number of Patients with Early Clinical Improvement: ivermectin+doxycycline (n= 111/183, 60.7%) placebo (n=80/180, 44.4%), HR= 0.53; CI 0.3-0.96; p< 0.03)
 - Number of Participants with Late Clinical Recovery (12 days): ivermectin+doxycycline (n= 42/183, 23%) placebo (n=67/180, 37.2%), HR=0.51; CI 0.32-0.8; p<0.004)
 - Number of Patients Having Clinical Deterioration: ivermectin+doxycycline (n= 16/183, 8.7%) placebo (n= 32/180, 17.8%), HR=0.45; CI 0.23-0.85; p<0.013)
 - Number of Patients Remain Persistently Positive for RT-PCR of Covid-19: ivermectin+doxycycline (n= 14/183, 7.7%) placebo (n=36/180, 20%), HR=0.44; CI 0.44-0.81; p<0.001)

⁴ <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/results/NCT04523831>

⁵ <https://www.banglajol.info/index.php/JBCPS/article/view/47514>

- All-cause mortality: ivermectin+doxycycline (n= 0/183, 0%) placebo (n=3/180, 1.67%), no statistics provided
- Comments:
 - Not yet peer-reviewed
 - No methodology to understand the effect of ivermectin vs doxycycline.
 - Small study without details on blinding or randomisation. The description of baseline characteristics is also limited. Hence there is little assurance if randomisation led to similar patient groups across study arms.
 - The ITT analysis is not provided. With a small trial like this, the exclusion of patients can make a big difference.

Gorial et al., 2020: RCT (not peer-reviewed pre-print;):

- Study design: single centre (Al-Shifa'a Hospital Center), non-randomised, most likely open-label trial
- Population:
 - mild to moderate COVID-19 patients without evidence of viral pneumonia or hypoxia
 - Methods n=30 (1:1 split)
 - In practice: n=86; 16 patients included in ivermectin arm, 71 included in control arm. No reason as to why.
 - mean age \pm SD (range) of patients in the IVM group was similar to controls [44.87 \pm 10.64 (28-60) vs 45.23 \pm 18.47 (8-80) years, p=0.78]. Majority of patients in both groups were male but statistically not significant [11(69%) versus 52 (73%), with male: female ratio 2.21 versus 2.7-, p=0.72)
- Interventions/control:
 - ivermectin 200 μ g single dose at the admission day as add on therapy to standard of care including hydroxychloroquine and azithromycin
 - synthetic control, unclear if it allowed for blinding
- Outcomes:
 - Primary outcome was percentage of cured patients, defined as symptoms free to be discharged from the hospital and 2 consecutive negative PCR test from nasopharyngeal swabs at least 24 hours apart.
 - Secondary outcomes were time to cure in both groups and evaluated by measuring time from admission of the patient to the hospital till discharge
- Results
 - Mean time to stay in the hospital (days): ivermectin versus control (7.62 \pm 2.75 versus 13.22 \pm .90 days, p=0.00005, effect size= 0.82).
 - Median days of positive PCR: ivermectin vs control [7 (95% CI 6-11) vs 12 (95% CI 10-15), log rank test p<0.001 respectively]
 - Two patients died in the controls
 - No adverse events were observed
- Comments
 - Not yet peer-reviewed
 - Small study without blinding or randomisation. The description of baseline characteristics is also limited.
 - Uncertainty as to why control arm is much larger without being pre-specified.

- Effect size is small (0.82 days shorter hospital stay)

Szente Fonseca et al, 2020: Observational study:

- Study design: Analysis of electronic charts Hapvida Saúde, the largest Brazilian health maintenance organization with 6 million members spread over five regions of the country.
- Population: SARS-CoV-2-positive patients age 40 years or older presenting in emergency room (n= 717)
- Interventions:
 - hydroxychloroquine as first-line treatment (400 mg bd day 1, 400 mg qd days 2–5)
 - prednisone (1 mg/kg qd x 5 days, maximum 80 mg/day, no taper)
 - azithromycin (500 mg qd x 5 days)
 - ivermectin (12 mg qd x 2 days)
 - Zinc sulphate, oseltamivir and nitazoxanide were also available to be prescribed but were used infrequently
- Control: none
- Outcome:
 - Associations between treatments and eventual hospitalization
 - Use of hydroxychloroquine, prednisone or both significantly reduced hospitalization risk by 50–60%.
 - The add-on of ivermectin, azithromycin and oseltamivir did not substantially reduce risk further

Camprubí et al., 2020: observational study

- Study design: retrospective study in severe patients of Hospital Clinic in Barcelona between March 10th and 30th 2020
- Population: 13 severe COVID-19 patients from countries endemic for *Strongyloides stercoralis* receiving immunosuppressant drugs such as corticosteroids or tocilizumab for COVID-19
- Interventions:
 - ivermectin 200µg/kg (single dose)
 - ivermectin was administered a median of 12 (IQR 8–18) days after the onset of symptoms
- Control: equal number of COVID-19 patients with similar baseline characteristics and immunosuppressive treatment but not receiving ivermectin
- Outcome:
 - No relevant differences in microbiological or clinical outcomes between groups.
 - SARS-CoV-2 PCR from nasopharyngeal swabs at 3- and 5-days post ivermectin: 5/13 positive ivermectin vs 4/13 in the control group

Rajter et al., 2020: observational study

- Study design: Retrospective review of charts of consecutive patients hospitalized at four Broward Health hospitals in Florida with confirmed COVID-19 between March 15 and May 11,

2020. Methodology allowed for adjusted analysis (to remove confounders) and propensity matching in a sub-cohort.

- Population:
 - Hospitalised patients with confirmed COVID-19
 - 280 patients in total, 173 treated with ivermectin and 107 without ivermectin
- Interventions: at least one oral dose of ivermectin at 200 µg/kg in addition to usual clinical care. A second dose could be given at day 7 of treatment. Most patients received a single dose of ivermectin; however, 13 patients received a second dose of ivermectin for ongoing signs or symptoms on day 7 of treatment.
- Control: patients not receiving ivermectin, propensity matching was performed in a sub-cohort
- Outcome:
 - Raw data:
 - Lower mortality in the ivermectin group (15.0% vs 25.2%; OR, 0.52; 95% CI, 0.29-0.96; P = .03).
 - No significant differences in extubation rates (36.1% vs 15.4%; OR, 3.11; 95% CI, 0.88-11.00; P = .07) or length of stay.
 - Multivariate adjustment (confounders and mortality risks) confirmed results from raw data (OR, 0.27; 95% CI, 0.09-0.80; P = .03).
 - Propensity-matched cohort (n=169) confirmed above results on mortality (13.3% vs 24.5%; OR, 0.47; 95% CI, 0.22-0.99; P < .05), an 11.2% (95% CI, 0.38%-22.1%) absolute risk reduction, with a number needed to treat of 8.9 (95% CI, 4.5-263).

5. Safety and drug interactions

Ivermectin has a well-understood safety profile due to its authorisations in UK for dermal application and international authorisations as oral administration.

There is no contraindication except hypersensitivity to active substance or excipients.

There is need for caution in breastfeeding women due to small amounts found in breastmilk.

Reported side effects associated with the oral dosing as anthelmintic include peripheral and facial oedema, (mainly orthostatic hypotension), tachycardia, worsening of bronchial asthma, toxic epidermal necrolysis, Stevens-Johnson syndrome, seizures, hepatitis, elevation of liver enzymes, and elevation of bilirubin, asthenia/fatigue, abdominal pain, constipation, diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting, dizziness, somnolence, vertigo, tremor, pruritus, rash, and urticaria.

In vitro studies have shown that ivermectin is primarily metabolised by CYP3A4. Consequently, caution is advised when ivermectin is administered concomitantly with potent CYP3A4 inhibitors as the plasma exposure may be significantly increased. Post-marketing reports of increased INR (International Normalized Ratio, prothrombin time) have been rarely reported when ivermectin was co-administered with warfarin.

High doses are well tolerated in both adults and children, and up to 10 times the licence dose has been tested in escalating dose trial in healthy adults (Guzzo et al., 2002), but even the highest dose from this experiment might not suffice for antiviral efficacy (see above).

6. Product availability and manufacturing

Figure 8: Structure of Ivermectin (Campbell, 2016)

[REMAINDER OF SECTION REDACTED FOR COMMERCIAL SENSITIVITY]

7. Suitability for different COVID-19 stages and trial platforms

7.1. Pre/Post exposure prophylaxis (e.g. PROTECT, PRINCIPLE)

- The clinically feasible plasma concentrations of ivermectin are unlikely to effectively inhibit SARS-CoV-2 virus. No clinical evidence yet in this setting of COVID-19
- Overall, acceptable safety profile in high doses (120 mg single dose, which is up to 10 times the highest FDA-approved dose of 200 microg/kg)
- Caution in breastfeeding women
- Caution is required in terms of poly-pharmacy due to its metabolism via CYP3A4.

7.2. Hospitalised patients (e.g. RECOVERY trial, AGILE trial)

- The clinically achievable plasma concentrations of ivermectin are unlikely to effectively inhibit SARS-CoV-2 virus
- Low quality preliminary clinical evidence of ivermectin in COVID-19 suggests either small or no relevant effects of the addition of ivermectin to current standard of care in mild to moderate disease.
- Overall, acceptable safety profile in high doses (120 mg single dose, which is up to 10 times the highest FDA-approved dose of 200 microg/kg)
- Caution is required in terms of poly-pharmacy due to its metabolism via CYP3A4. For example, concurrent dexamethasone as potent inducer of CYP3A4 (in severe COVID-19 setting) would influence the PK and lead to increased metabolism and reduced drug exposure of ivermectin.

7.3. Severe hospitalised patients (e.g. REMAP-CAP trial)

- The clinically feasible plasma concentrations of ivermectin are unlikely to effectively inhibit SARS-CoV-2 virus

- No clinical evidence yet in this setting of COVID-19
- Overall, acceptable safety profile in high doses (120 mg single dose, which is up to 10 times the highest FDA-approved dose of 200 microg/kg)
- Caution is required in terms of poly-pharmacy due to its metabolism via CYP3A4. Especially in this setting, dexamethasone as potent inducer of CYP3A4 (in severe COVID-19 setting) would influence the PK and lead to increased metabolism and reduced drug exposure of ivermectin.

8. Regulatory considerations and clinical trial environment

8.1. Current clinical trial environment:

- There are 24 ongoing randomised controlled trials and 2 non-randomised trials investigating ivermectin.
- Ongoing randomised controlled trials are enrolling over 4,000 patients with mild, moderate and severe disease.
- Of the trials recruiting, 25 investigate ivermectin as a treatment and 2 investigate ivermectin for prevention.
- Trials include ivermectin in combination with azithromycin, cholecalciferol, doxycycline, nigella sativa, zinc, iota-carrageenan, losartan and chloroquine.
- Trials that have completed with no results include a further 3 treatment trials and 3 treatment trials.
- There are currently no trials in the UK

8.2. Dosing in trials

In the online trial protocols, there are two ways of dose calculations:

1. Weight based: mostly around 300µg/kg, range from 200µg/kg – 1200 µg/kg
2. Not weight based: mostly around 12mg, range from 6mg-24mg
3. Duration: most commonly a single administration, but some trials will also administer over periods

9. Annex 1: regulatory information (BNF, SmPC, HMA, WHO)

9.1. Pharmaceutical forms:

Authorised UK:

- Soolantra 10mg/g Cream from marketing authorisation holder Galderma (U.K) Ltd.

Imported from France (off-label use; generics available across Europe):

- Stromectol 3mg tablets

WHO essential medicines:

- 6.1.1 Intestinal anthelmintics: Tablet (scored): 3 mg

9.2. Indication

Authorised UK:

Ivermectin (Soolantra cream) is indicated for the topical treatment of inflammatory lesions of rosacea (papulopustular) in adult patients.

Off-label (Stromectol France and EU generics):

- Treatment of gastrointestinal strongyloidiasis (anguillulosis).
- Treatment of suspected or diagnosed microfilaraemia in patients with lymphatic filariasis due to *Wuchereria bancrofti*.
- Treatment of human sarcoptic scabies.
- Treatment is justified when the diagnosis of scabies has been established clinically and/or by parasitological examination. Without formal diagnosis treatment is not justified in case of pruritus.

9.3. Posology

Authorised topical:

One application a day for up to 4 months. Soolantra should be applied daily over the treatment course. The treatment course may be repeated. It can be applied as monotherapy or as part of combination treatment.

Off-label oral:

- Chronic Strongyloides infection: 200 micrograms/kg daily for 2 days (oral, adults)
- Onchocerciasis: 150 micrograms/kg for 1 dose, retreatment at intervals of 6 to 12 months, depending on symptoms, must be given until the adult worms die out. (oral, adults)
- Scabies, in combination with topical drugs, for the treatment of hyperkeratotic (crusted or 'Norwegian') scabies that does not respond to topical treatment alone: 200 micrograms/kg for 1 dose, further doses of 200 micrograms/kg may be required. (oral, adults)

9.4. Clinical Pharmacokinetics

Ivermectin plasma PK was measured in Kenyan adults with uncomplicated malaria treated with 300 µg/kg PO QD for 3 days (Figure 9e) or 600 µg/kg PO QD for 3 days (Figure 9f). These data were fitted to 2-compartment oral PK model.

The model was reproduced and simulated to repeat those data (Figure 10).

Figure 9. Ivermectin plasma PK in adults with uncomplicated malaria in Kenya. e) 300µg/kg PO QD for 3 days. f) 600µg/kg PO QD for 3 days. Dots: data from patients in Kenya. Lines: expected values together with 5%-95% percentiles by model simulation (1000 patients were sampled, assuming bodyweight is in range of 45-101kg with a median 60kg). Shaded area: 95% confidence intervals of the expected values or percentiles. The figure is taken from Smit et al, 2019.

Figure 10. Simulation of ivermectin plasma PK (ng/mL) in adults with uncomplicated malaria in Kenya. 1000 patients were sampled using Latin Hypercube method, assuming bodyweight is in range of 45-101kg with a median of 60kg. A) 300µg/kg

PO QD for 3 days. B) 600µg/kg PO QD for 3 days. Red line: expected values. Black lines: 5%-95% percentiles. The 2-compartment model was reproduced from Smit et al, 2019. Parameters were tabulated in the middle column of Table 1 in that paper (i.e. "Ivermectin simultaneous PK/PD model").

9.5. Contraindication:

No contraindication except hypersensitivity to active substance or excipients.

9.6. Caution:

- Breastfeeding: Limited published evidence of safety, Small amounts in breast milk

9.7. Interaction:

- In vitro studies have shown that ivermectin is primarily metabolised by CYP3A4. Consequently, caution is advised when ivermectin is administered concomitantly with potent CYP3A4 inhibitors as the plasma exposure may be significantly increased.
- Concomitant treatment with diethylcarbamazine citrate (DEC) and ivermectin in mass chemotherapy campaigns for filariasis caused by *Wuchereria Bancrofti* in Africa is not recommended. Systemic exposure to DEC in such patients may result in the occurrence of serious side effects related to the rapid and effective microfilaricidal effects of this drug. These reactions are probably due to inflammatory responses to degradation products released following the death of microfilariae.

9.8. Side effects:

Common or very common:

- Skin reactions

Unknown frequency:

abnormal sensation in eye; anaemia; appetite decreased; asthenia; asthma exacerbated; chest discomfort; coma; confusion; conjunctival haemorrhage; constipation; diarrhoea; difficulty standing; difficulty walking; dizziness; drowsiness; dyspnoea; encephalopathy; eosinophilia; eye inflammation; faecal incontinence; fever; gastrointestinal discomfort; headache; hepatitis; hypotension; joint disorders; leukopenia; lymphatic abnormalities; Mazzotti reaction aggravated; myalgia; nausea; oedema; pain; psychiatric disorder; seizure; severe cutaneous adverse reactions (SCARs); stupor; tachycardia; tremor; urinary incontinence; vertigo; vomiting

10. Annex 2: Antiviral effects of Ivermectin in SARS-CoV-2

10.1. Antiviral activity

There is evidence that Ivermectin has broad antiviral activity mainly through inhibition of host proteins which allow viral influx to cell nuclei, particularly the importin alpha/beta1 and integrase proteins. Antiviral activity of Ivermectin has been demonstrated in a number of viral diseases, including coronaviridae.

Virus	Inhibitory Concentration/Fold reduction (Assay)
Coronavirus:	EC50 = 2.2/2.8 µM/5000-fold reduction (qPCR:released/cell-associated virus) [17]
SARS-CoV-2	[17]
Lentivirus:	50 µM > 2-fold reduction (luciferase) [7]
HIV-1 (VSV-G-pseudotyped NL4-3.Luc.R-E-HIV)	10 µM total inhibition (luciferase) [10]
Orthomyxovirus	EC50 = 5/0.5 nM (CPE/qPCR) [12] 3 µM > 50,000-fold reduction (pfu) [15]
Influenza VLPs (avian influenza A/MxA escape mutants)	EC50 = 2.3/3 µM (CFI, 2 hosts) [8] EC50 = 0.7 µM (qPCR) [12] EC50 = 0.4/0.6 µM (pfu/qPCR) [11] 50 µM total inhibition (pfu) [7]
Flavivirus:	
YFV (17D)	EC50 = 2.1/1.7 µM (CFI, 2 hosts) [8]
DENV1 (EDEN-1)	EC50 = 1.7 µM (CFI) [8]
DENV2 (NGC)	EC50 = 1.9 µM (CFI) [8]
DENV2 (EDEN-2)	EC50 = 4 µM (qPCR) [12]
DENV3 (EDEN-3)	EC50 = 1.0.5 µM (pfu/qPCR) [11]
DENV4 (EDEN-4)	EC50 = 1.3/1.6 µM (pfu/qPCR) [11]
WNV (NY99)	EC50 = 1.9/0.6 µM (luciferase, 2 hosts) 3 µM > 5000-fold reduction (pfu) [15]
WNV (MRM61C)	[15]
ZIKV (Asian/Cook Islands/2014)	3 µM > 1000-fold (pfu) [15]
Alphavirus:	
Chikungunya virus (CHIKV-Rluc)	1 µM c. 20-fold (pfu) [5]
Sindbis (HR)	est. EC50 = 2 µM (TCID/luciferase) [13]
Semliki Forest Virus	EC50 = c. 2.5 µM; 10 µM 20-fold reduction (qPCR) [20]
VEEV (TC83)	10 µM c. 8-fold reduction (qPCR) [20]
Henipavirus:	
Hendra (Hendra virus/Australia/Horse/1994)	Est. EC50 1.5 µM (pfu/CPE/qPCR) [19]
DNA viruses	
Adenovirus (HAdV-C5)	
Adenovirus (HAdV-B3)	
BK polyomavirus (BKPvV)	
Pseudorabies	

Abbreviations: HIV-1, human immunodeficiency virus; VLP, virus like particle; PSV, Pseudorabies virus; YFV (yellow fever virus); DENV, dengue virus; ZIKV, zika virus; WNV, West Nile virus; TCID, pfu, plaque forming unit (infectious virus assay); CPE, cytopathic effects; qPCR, quantitative polymerase chain reaction; CFI, cell fluorescence-based immunofluorescence assay.

^b Inhibits helicase activity (FRET based assay) of DENV2, YFV and WNV NS3 (IC50 0.2–0.5 µM) [12].

Table 2: Documented antiviral action of ivermectin (in vitro)

In vitro Ivermectin selectively inhibits the shuttling of the SARS-CoV2 viral nucleocapsid protein (NCP) into the host nucleus via the nuclear pore complex by blocking the importin alpha/beta1 transporter protein (Caly et al, 2020). The nuclear pore complex is a multimeric structure comprised of numerous proteins which form a trans membrane pore allowing selective transport of proteins from the cytoplasm into the nucleus. This pore complex is hijacked by numerous viruses for entry into the nucleus including adeno virus, herpes simplex, influenza A, HIV and hepatitis B. The importin proteins form a dimer which binds to the cargo transported across the pore complex and in its dimeric form activates ran/gtp in the nuclear space permitting transport and release of cargo into the nucleus. Ivermectin binds to and prevents dimerization of the importin molecules preventing cargo transport across the pore. Viral particles reliant on the pore complex are therefore inhibited from nuclear entry by Ivermectin at appropriate concentrations (Wagstaff et al., 2012).

Figure 11: Ivermectin mechanism of action

SARS-CoV2 nucleocapsid protein is released into the cytoplasm when the virus enters the cell and relies on the pore complex to be transported into the nucleus where host replication machinery is co-opted for viral replication. When tested *in vitro*, Ivermectin concentrations of 5 μM (twice the IC50) resulted in reduction of viral RNA load by 99.98% at 48h (Caly, 2020). That study forms the basis for most optimism regarding the use of the drug in SARS-CoV2.

In silico studies have also shown Ivermectin has a high binding affinity with RNA dependant polymerase (Sen Gupta et al., 2020) and possibly the spike protein of SARS-CoV2. How much of a role each of these plays in blocking the viral integration and expression is unknown, and no *in vitro* studies or x-ray crystallography studies have been done to confirm the computational findings.

10.2. Antiviral effects in the context of syncytia formation

The evidence in this section has been derived from a manuscript that is available to the UK-CTAP due diligence team. The manuscript is currently under review.

The authors suggest that the mechanism of action of syncytia formation is likely due to the expression and activation of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein on the cell membrane of the infected cell. Approximately 3000 approved medicines were screened through two independent high throughput microscopy-based assays to identify inhibitors of spike-driven syncytia. 83 medicines were identified in these two assays. 9 compounds were identified through both assays. A Venn diagram is presented in the manuscript that shows identified medicines (Figure 12). This list contains ivermectin, and the manuscript highlights the fact that ivermectin was also chosen to be further screened in subsequent *in vitro* SARS-CoV-2 infection assays. Results are presented from a cell viability assay, in which Vero6 cells were preincubated with 10 μM for 2 hours before 100 TCID50 of SARS-CoV-2/England/IC19/2020 was added. While there is only graphical representation of the cell toxicity, it seems that the treatment with 10 μM did not protect cells of SARS-CoV-2 induced cell mortality to a high degree, (Figure 14) which casts down on the clinical relevance of any inhibitory effect on syncytia formation. This conclusion is supported by the PK data shown in the following sections which demonstrates plasma concentrations of around 100nm are achievable.

Figure 12: Identification of inhibitors of spike-driven syncytia (full text of the manuscript available from the due diligence team)

Figure 13: SARS-CoV-2 infection of Vero 6 cells with 10μM of medicines including ivermectin. Cell survivability is depicted (full text of the manuscript available from the due diligence team)

10.3. Pharmacology (Anti-viral)

The dose required to reach target organ concentrations of 5 μM seems unachievable. The highest reported single dose of 1700 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (8.5 times the approved dose of 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, given in dose escalation study) resulted in plasma concentration of 0.28 μM and Ivermectin is significantly plasma protein bound, which will limit its cellular uptake.

Calves dosed with 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ only managed to get to 100 ng/g (0.1 μM) of the drug in lung tissue suggesting it is unlikely to penetrate lung well enough.

Modelled lung concentrations even at very high doses appear to be too low to be effective as well (Jermain et al., 2020).

A case series of 3 paediatric patients describe high dose continuous use of the drug at 1 mg/kg without side effects (de Castro Jr. et al., 2020).

- In contrast, *in vitro* anti-viral IC_{50} was reported to be around 2.5 μM , which was approximately an order-of-magnitude higher than the clinically achievable concentrations (Caly et al, 2020, Figure 14)
- Hence, it is unlikely that ivermectin would effectively reduce viral load in patients. This point was previously highlighted by (Chaccour, Hammann, et al., 2020) and was also recognised by the NIH.

“However, pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies suggest that achieving the plasma concentrations necessary for the antiviral efficacy detected *in vitro* would require administration of doses up to 100-fold higher than those approved for use in humans.^{8,9} Even though ivermectin appears to accumulate in the lung tissue, predicted systemic plasma and lung tissue concentrations are much lower than 2 μM , the half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) against SARS-CoV-2 *in vitro*.^{10,11}”

Figure 14. Ivermectin inhibits SARS-CoV-2 clinical isolate Australia/VIC01/2020 *in vitro*. Vero/hSLAM cells were infected with SARS-CoV-2 clinical isolate Australia/VIC01/2020 (MOI = 0.1) for 2 h prior to addition of vehicle (DMSO) or Ivermectin at the indicated concentrations. IC_{50} values were determined *in vitro* at 48 h post infection using the indicated concentrations of Ivermectin (treated at 2 h post infection). Triplicate real-time PCR analysis was performed on cell associated virus (C/E) or supernatant (D/F) using probes against either the SARS-CoV-2 E (C/D) or RdRp (E/F) genes. Results represent mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). 3 parameter dose response curves were fitted using GraphPad prism to determine IC_{50} values (indicated). Figure is taken from Caly et al 2020.

⁶ <https://www.covid19treatmentguidelines.nih.gov/antiviral-therapy/ivermectin/>

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